

Computational simulation of electromagnetic fields on human targets for magnetic targeting applications

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Abstract— In the last few years, the use of nanoparticles for therapeutic applications has attracted the interest of many scientists, who are looking for effective methods to target nanoparticles linked to drugs directly to the diseased organs. Among them, magnetic targeting consists of magnetic systems (magnets or coils) which can impress high gradient magnetic fields and then magnetic forces on the magnetic nanoparticles. Despite some studies have reported an effective improvement in drug delivery by using this technique, there is still a paucity of studies able to quantify and explain the experimental results. In this scenario, “in silico” models allow to analyze and compare different magnetic targeting systems in their ability to generate the required magnetic field gradient for specific human targets.

In this paper we then evaluated, by means of computational electromagnetics techniques, the attitude of various ad-hoc designed magnetic systems in targeting the heart tissues of differently aged human anatomical models

I. INTRODUCTION

Magnetic targeting is a promising technique in which magnetically responsive micro or nanoparticles (NPs), linked to specific drugs are released into the blood and then focused to target locations into the body by means of externally applied high gradient magnetic fields [1][2] administered through magnets or coils. This allows to concentrate the drugs to disease sites while keeping low systemic concentrations and thus minimizing side effects [3]. Since the magnetically responsive particles must “extravasate” (i.e. passing from blood vessels to the target tissue) their typical radius range between 1 nm-5 μm [4]. This dimension limits the maximum force that can be impressed on them, with a maximum in the order of piconewton (10^{-12}) when the target is close to the magnetic field source [4]. Magnetic force scales indeed with particle volume and rapidly decrease with distance from the source. In parallel, when in the blood flow magnetic NPs are subject to drag forces that, in turn, scale with particle radius. So far, the detailed analysis of the magnetic force that magnetic targeting systems can generate in the human body is still limited, and so is the diffusion of these systems for applications on humans. However, they started to be successfully used on small animals [5]-[10].

The results of the few applications conducted in humans [11]-[13] have qualitatively shown that, under particular conditions, magnetic forces can focus nanoparticles in-vivo near magnets.

However, the mechanism behind this accumulation (i.e. which vessels magnetic forces have exceeded blood drag forces, where in the vessel accumulation is occurring...) cannot be investigated experimentally but only “in silico” using mathematical simulations.

From the magnetic point of view, computational based approaches offer the advantage to analyze and compare the suitability of different systems to generate the required magnetic gradient and allow to optimize magnetic sources for specific drug targeting applications [14]-[16].

A still little explored target for magnetic nanoparticle deposition and concentration in the human body is represented by heart tissues, which instead could be a strategic organ, given the large prevalence of cardiovascular and heart diseases worldwide. To this purpose, in the last few years some authors have explored the possibility to deliver nanocarriers conjugated to cardiac drugs to the infarcted heart [17]-[19], to prevent heart failure [20] to protect the endothelium [21] and the cardiovascular system [22].

Then, in this paper we evaluated, by means of computational electromagnetics techniques, the attitude of various ad-hoc designed magnetic systems in targeting the heart tissues of differently aged human anatomical models.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Magnetic targeting system (MTS) modelling

In this work we considered the simplest and most commonly used system for magnetic targeting applications, which is based on permanent magnets. The strongest commercially available permanent magnet can reach a residual magnetism (or remanence B_r) up to 1.47 T and maximum dimensions, for disc magnets, of 15-20 cm (diameter). In order to explore the suitability of a MTS based on electromagnets, we focused first on magnets based systems and then we calculated the current needed in coils of the same dimension to generate the same force of magnets.

B. Modelling of Magnetic fields and forces

The propagation through the space of magnetic fields generated by the MTS is described by Maxwell’s equation. For

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static and slowly time-varying magnetic fields the magneto quasi static approximation is applied

$$\nabla \times \vec{H} = \vec{j} \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{B} = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\vec{B} = \mu_0(\vec{H} + \vec{M}) = \mu_0(\vec{H} + \chi\vec{H}) \quad (3)$$

Where \vec{B} is the magnetic induction [in units of Tesla T], \vec{H} is the magnetic field [A/m], \vec{M} is the material magnetization [A/m], $\mu_0=4\pi \cdot 10^{-7}$ N/A² is the vacuum permeability, μ_r is the relative magnetic permeability and $\chi=\mu_r-1$ is the magnetic susceptibility. These equations hold both in vacuum and in materials and for permanent magnets (magnetization $\vec{M} \neq 0$) and electromagnets (current $\vec{j} \neq 0$) and have been numerically solved through the magneto static solver as implemented by simulation platform CST EM Studio [CST, Darmstadt, Germany] and through the magneto quasi-static solver of simulation platform SEMCAD X [by SPEAG, Zurich, Switzerland]-

Magnetic fields pass virtually unchanged through the human tissues because their magnetic susceptibility χ ($= \mu-1$) is close to zero. In contrast, the cores of ferromagnetic NPs have magnetic susceptibilities several orders of magnitude higher than that of tissues, producing strong interactions with magnetic fields. Magnetic force on a single spherical NP/NP agglomerate depends on both magnetic field and magnetic field gradient created at its location and is given by:

$$\vec{F}_M = \frac{4\pi a^3}{3} \frac{\mu_0 \chi}{(1+\frac{\chi}{3})} \vec{H} \frac{d\vec{H}}{d\vec{x}} = \frac{2\pi a^3}{3} \frac{\mu_0 \chi}{(1+\frac{\chi}{3})} \nabla(|\vec{H}|^2) \quad (1)$$

Where a is the radius of the NP, $\vec{x}=(x,y,z)$ is its location, and $\nabla=(\frac{d}{dx}, \frac{d}{dy}, \frac{d}{dz})$ is the spatial gradient operator.

F_m distribution was calculated from magnetic field distribution through a MATLAB [The MathWorks, Natick, MA] code.

B. Target area definition

The distribution of magnetic field and magnetic forces was calculated on the heart of five different human anatomical models (Fig.1) belonging to the Virtual Population [23][24] made available for research purpose from IT'IS Foundation (Zurich, Switzerland).

Up to 84 tissues are distinguished in all models and at the heart level, heart lumen, heart muscle (myocardium) and largest blood vessels.

Target area is defined by the minimum distance D , as calculated along the magnetic system axis center (z) and considering the axis origin ($x,y,z=0$) at the center of the MTS attached to the skin (Fig. 1). It is highly variable on anatomy, ranging between 13.5 and 31.5 mm as summarized in Table 1.

C. Magnetic targeting system and simulation details summary

Bearing in mind that the MTS is thought to act on heart tissues, its dimensions are chosen accordingly. In order to avoid NPs being attracted by the magnet before reaching the hearth, the maximum system diameter was set to be lower than the maximum heart dimension in the coronal (in the following

Figure 1 Target area definition in human (left) and Virtual Population models (right).

TABLE I. TARGET AREA DISTANCE OF EACH ANATOMICAL MODEL

Model Name	Gender	Age (Y)	D_{target} (mm)
Thelonious	Male	6	13.5
Eartha	Female	8	16
Louis	Male	14	18
Ella	Female	26	31.5
Glenn	Male	84	25

x - y) plane. The examined MTSs consists in a single disc magnet/round coil, given that the shape does not substantially change the final results (data not shown). They are therefore modelled as circular magnet of radius ranging between $R_{\text{magnet}} = 10$ -80 mm.

A uniform axial permanent magnetization $B_r=1.47$ T was set in the simulation according to the maximum B_r of commercially available magnets. This results in a maximum magnetic field induction at the central point of the upper face magnet center $B_{\text{center}}=0.735$ T when the height of the magnets is substantially higher than its radius. Current in a single loop ($N=1$) of the same radius of the magnet was calculated to have the same B_{center} at the current loop center, through the well-known Biot-Savart equation:

Figure 2 Gradient of squared magnetic field (A^2/m^3) exerted on the NP agglomerate at the target distance of different human models as a function of single magnet based system radius (R_{magnet})

$$NI = \frac{2R_{coil}B_{center}}{\mu_0} \quad (5)$$

Magnetic systems are placed on the skin at the heart level, with the centre at the level of the heart centre and a minimum distance from the heart surface as listed in Table 2. Computational domain was discretized using a uniform rectilinear mesh grid of 0.5 mm. The magnetic field distribution in the space interposed by the magnetic system was extracted from the mesh and then imported in MATLAB to calculate $\nabla(|H|^2)$.

This last quantity, and the corresponding magnetic force, at distance even shorter than the system radius, can be considered almost constant and directed mainly perpendicular to its surface. That is even truer at higher distance, in particular at a distance equal to the target area distance, i.e. in the small blood vessel area. Therefore, for the sake of simplicity, in the following we refer to F_m and $\nabla(|H|^2)$, unless otherwise specified, as directed along z.

III. RESULTS

As discussed above, the analysis of the magnetic system is limited to single disc magnet and corresponding equivalent coil. Given the different target distances across human models, the best magnet based solution varies as shown in Figure 2, where the maximum gradient of squared magnetic field calculated for each model and for variable magnet radii is represented.

We then calculated the current supplied to the coil based system in order to produce the maximum gradient of squared magnetic field calculated for magnets. Given that current increases linearly with coil radius, there are case in which is convenient using a coil with a smaller radius even if the peak of the gradient at the D_{target} was found for a larger system radius. In this case Table 2 lists the minimum current needed to reach the best gradient of squared magnetic field by together with the corresponding best coil, in terms of radius option, to supply with that current magnets.

TABLE II. SUMMARY OF THE HUMAN MODELS ANALYSIS

Model Name	Best R_{magnet} solution (mm)	MAX $\nabla(H ^2)$ (A^2/m^3)	MIN I (kA·turn) in the coil (R_{coil}) such as $\nabla(H ^2)$ @ $D_{target} =$ MAX $\nabla(H ^2)$	Best R_{coil} solution (mm)
Thelonious	30	1.02E+13	8.27	15
Eartha	40	8.61E+12	9.74	15
Louis	45	7.65E+12	11.03	20
Ella	75	4.38E+12	19.15	30
Glenn	60	5.52E+12	15.10	25

In particular, in children and adolescents, disc magnets with radii up to 5 cm can produce a maximum gradient of squared magnetic field ranging between about 0.8 and $1.0 \cdot 10^{13}$ A^2/m^3 . This magnitude, according to our calculation and considering a NP magnetic susceptibility equal to 20 (as for magnetite), is able to compete with the drag force at the equilibrium ($F_d = 6\pi\eta a v_b$, where η is the blood viscosity, here 3 mPa·s, and v_b is the blood velocity), for all the combination of NP radius and blood velocity below the curve (blue area) shown in the following figure (Figure 3).

Figure 3 Combination of nanoparticle ($\chi=20$) radius a , and blood velocity v_b , which allow to produce a magnetic force equals to the blood force at the equilibrium when the NP are subjected to a gradient of squared magnetic field equals to $1.0 \cdot 10^{13}$ A^2/m^3

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Magnetic drug delivery is a fascinating technique, whose efficacy has already been proven both in animals and in some few human trials, but its utility has been limited to targets near the external surface of the human [5]-[13]. This is mainly due to both practical and physical factors. The scarce knowledge of the detailed anatomy in individual patients makes indeed hard to define exactly the target of the treatment. Moreover, according to Earnshaw theorem, there is no way to apply external magnets to create a magnetic trap deep inside the body, while electromagnets based systems would require a closed loop control together with a strong current supply. On the other hand, the amplitude of the magnetic force exerted by any magnetic system rapidly decays with distance, thus limiting the area where those forces can compete with the drag force. The constraint on the spatial geometry of the magnetic field with respect to the target site has posed great difficulty in moving from animal studies to clinical trials. In this scenario, computational methods, both in electromagnetics and fluid transport modelling, could be a powerful tool in determining and optimizing MTS. From the magnetic side, subject of this report, they indeed allow to provide a detailed analysis of the magnetic fields distribution in the target tissues generated by different systems and then to find the optimal technical solution for variable human anatomy.

In this paper we compared, with the purpose of finding the optimal system for the magnetic targeting of super paramagnetic nanoparticles to the heart, the behaviour of different systems based on magnets/coils placed on various human models, by calculating the squared magnetic field distribution, which is proportional to the magnetic force.

The results of the analysis of the optimum dimension for a single disc magnet system indicate first of all that the designed system should be finely calibrated on the basis of anatomy: the behaviour of the peak of magnetic field gradient, for a given distance and for a specific model, is

achieved with different system radii as clearly illustrated in Figure 2.

As expected, for children and adolescents, where the target distances are shorter, smaller systems allow to produce even double magnetic field gradients (and, equivalently, magnetic forces) compared to the best systems for adults. On the other hand, larger systems allow to reach deeper targets and broader areas.

However, the scarce availability and the substantial encumbrance of single magnet based systems larger than 10 cm would encourage to explore other solutions, such as systems based on coils. As detailed in the fourth column of Table 2, the current supply needed to reach the same forces as coils, is higher than $1.5 \cdot 10^4 \text{ A} \cdot \text{turn}$, which pose a limit on the system feasibility.

Results of this study suggest that a reasonable (and chosen in this study) scope for magnetic drug delivery on human heart is to approach as much as possible drag force in superficial capillaries and near the blood vessels wall, where velocity are slower, rather than try to compete with the stronger forces in the centre of larger blood vessels and this is true particularly for small particles (Figure 3). This is in agreement with the studies of Nacev and colleagues [25] which stated that using the centerline blood velocity to estimate the drag forces dramatically overestimates these forces near the vessel walls, and thus severely under-predicts the ability of magnetic drug targeting to capture particles.

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